

Interesting influence of structure phases on hydrogen storage properties of AB₅ type alloys

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Bullet points:

- Substituting nickel with tin increases the unit cell volume, which lowers equilibrium plateau pressures and stabilizes the resulting hydrides.
- The coexistence of two LaNi₅-type phases within a miscibility gap leads to an increase in the slope of the plateau, but favorably reduces the pressure hysteresis.
- Alloys with higher lanthanum content exhibit a dual-phase microstructure (LaNi₅ and LaNiSn), resulting in a distinct two-step hydrogenation process.
- Incoherent grain boundaries in multiphase alloys significantly reduce activation energy by providing fast pathways for hydrogen diffusion.

Abstract

The impact of phase composition and Sn substitution to Ni on the hydrogen storage properties of La–Ni–Sn alloys is described in this paper. Through a combination of XRD, SEM and Sieverts-type measurements with ab initio calculations, we demonstrate that Sn substitution increases the unit cell volume, thereby lowering equilibrium plateau pressures and enhancing hydride stability. In alloys with 30 wt.% La, a miscibility gap causes the coexistence of two LaNi₅-type phases, leads to an increase in the slope of the plateau and reduced hysteresis. Alloys with 40 wt.% La exhibit a dual-phase microstructure (LaNi₅ and LaNiSn), resulting in two-step hydrogenation. Kinetic analysis via the JMAK model reveals that while the microstructure miscibility gap slows down the hydrogen absorption, the presence of incoherent grain boundaries in multiphase alloys significantly reduces activation energy (down to 15.1 kJ/mol) by facilitating faster Gb hydrogen diffusion. These results demonstrate that Gb diffusion could be a powerful tool for tuning the thermodynamic and kinetic performance of AB₅-type storage materials.

Keywords: Hydrogen storage, AB₅ alloys, LaNi₅, Sn substitution, PCT isotherms, Hydrogenation kinetics, Miscibility gap.

Introduction

The solid-state hydrogen storage (HS), particularly with metal hydrides, stands out for its superior volumetric density, inherent safety, and operational capability under moderate temperature and pressure conditions. Unlike gaseous or liquid hydrogen, which store hydrogen molecules (H_2) that experience repulsive interactions, metal hydrides store hydrogen as individual atoms, allowing for volumetric densities exceeding $90 \text{ kg } H_2/m^3$ [1,2]. This is a significant advantage over compressed hydrogen ($42 \text{ kg } H_2/m^3$ at 70.0 MPa) and liquid hydrogen ($70.6 \text{ kg } H_2/m^3$ at $-253 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) [3-5].

Within the broad spectrum of metal hydrides, AB_5 -type intermetallic compounds have emerged as a class of materials of immense interest for HS applications. These compounds are characterized by a stoichiometric ratio of one rare-earth element (A) to transition metal elements (B) and typically crystallize in a hexagonal $CaCu_5$ -type structure, with a $P6/mmm$ space group [6,7]. Their capacity to reversibly absorb and desorb hydrogen at near ambient temperatures and pressures makes them highly attractive for various uses, including the negative electrodes in nickel-metal hydride (NiMH) rechargeable batteries, as well as in hydrogen compressors and purification systems [8, 9].

This $LaNi_5$ -type compound however, exhibits intrinsic limitations that restrict its direct suitability for practical applications, particularly those requiring extensive cycling durability or carefully managed pressure conditions. $LaNi_5$ demonstrates a hydrogen equilibrium pressure p_{eq} that is too high for optimal technical applications, coupled with an unsatisfactorily poor cycle life [7]. These unsatisfied properties necessitate substantial material modification of these compounds, where La or Ni are partially substituted by other elements. The strategic goals of such substitutions allow to tune the equilibrium pressure to a range appropriate for technical applications and significantly enhance the cycling stability of these alloys [10].

The replacement of Co for Ni was extremely efficient in extending the cycle life of these substances. However, due to the high cost of Co, intense research efforts have focused on reducing its content in commercial batteries or finding economically viable substitute elements with comparable performance [11]. In this context, the partial substitution of Ni with Sn has emerged as a particularly promising strategy, demonstrating remarkable potential to enhance crucial alloy properties such as thermodynamic stability and the durability of the resulting hydride phase. Sn-substituted $LaNi_5$ alloys have been shown to endure thousands of cycles without a significant decline in hydrogen storage capacity. This enhanced durability, which is particularly evident in such compounds, often comes alongside improved kinetics and an extended cycle life [12, 13].

The beneficial effects of Sn substitution are fundamentally linked to the resulting changes in the crystal structure. $LaNi_5$ -based alloys typically crystallise in a hexagonal-type structure. Neutron and X-ray powder diffraction analyses have conclusively shown that tin atoms predominantly substitute nickel atoms on crystallographic sites in the median plane of the unit cell while largely avoiding the 2c

sites [14, 15]. This site preference is primarily determined by the larger atomic radius of tin (163 pm) compared to nickel (125 pm) [16]. The favored occupation of the 3g crystallographic site by the larger Sn atoms is hypothesized to stabilize the lattice by mechanically preventing structural instabilities, thereby promoting the observed long-term cyclic stability of the hydride [15].

The consequence of incorporating larger Sn atoms is a notable and typically linear expansion of the lattice parameters a and c , and consequently, a "huge cell volume increase" (V). This V change of the alloys $\text{LaNi}_{5-x}\text{Sn}_x$, is the dominant factor governing the resulting properties [17,18,19]. However, complexities arise in non-stoichiometric compositions, often described as $\text{La}_{1-y}\text{Sn}_y\text{Ni}_{5-x}\text{Sn}_x$, where Nickel atoms sometimes occupy lanthanum sites via dumbbell pairs distributed along the c -axis (over-stoichiometry) [20]. While increasing over-stoichiometry leads to a minor contraction in the cell volume, the major factor determining the unit cell dimension remains the Sn concentration. For instance, certain over-stoichiometric Sn alloys ($x \approx 0.4$) demonstrated a unit cell volume of 89.771 \AA^3 [16].

The changes in unit cell volume induced by Sn substitution profoundly impact the thermodynamic properties of the hydride [21]. According to established relationships, an increase in V leads to a decrease in the equilibrium plateau pressure (p_{eq}) for hydrogen absorption and desorption. The stabilising effect is significant: the equilibrium absorption pressure at room temperature (approximately 300 K) decreases from around 0.250 MPa for LaNi_5 to 0.085 MPa for $\text{LaNi}_{4.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}$ [22]. Thermodynamically, this corresponds to an increase in the absolute value of the enthalpy (ΔH) of hydride formation, indicating a more stable hydride [23].

A crucial correlation exists between Sn content and the relative volume expansion that occurs during the transformation from the α -phase (metallic solid solution) to the β -phase (hydride). LaNi_5 -based alloys with higher Sn concentrations exhibit a sharply reduced volume expansion of only 9–10%. This is approximately half of the 18–20% expansion observed in materials with lower Sn content [7]. This decreased lattice strain directly correlates with improved cycle stability [16]. For instance, doubling the tin content from 0.03 to 0.06 was found to double the observed cycle life stability, despite resulting in a modest 10% reduction in total hydrogen capacity (c_{max}^H). However, capacity generally decreases as over-stoichiometry and Sn content rise. Furthermore, the introduction of Sn reduces the hysteresis between the pressures of hydrogen absorption (p_a) and desorption (p_d) pressures, which is a desirable attribute for energy-efficient cycling [7].

In terms of kinetics, alloys exhibit fast hydrogen absorption rates. Studies show that the absorption time for $\text{LaNi}_{4.5}\text{Sn}_{0.5}$ can be remarkably fast, measuring below 2.5s at 0.750 MPa, far faster than the 1 min required for hydrogen absorption in the system, which is controlled by the diffusion of hydrogen atoms through the forming hydride layer rather than surface-related phenomena such as chemisorption. This suggests that Sn substitution does not dramatically alter the surface catalytic

activity required for hydrogen dissociation. An optimal Sn content of $x=0.42$ or $x=0.48$ provides superior overall electrochemical performance and maintains stability even when subjected to substantial charge/discharge currents [24].

While the HS of LaNiSn-type alloys has been widely studied, the La–Ni–Sn system contains a variety of intermetallic phases, making it a suitable model for studying the influence of different LaNiSn-based phases on HS properties (Figure 1). Currently it was found the miscibility gap in isothermal section of La-Ni-Sn phase diagram at 573K close to LaNi₅ phase, which could significantly influence the HS thermodynamic and kinetics properties [25].

Experimental

Preparation of experimental materials

The experimental materials were prepared using high-purity elements: La (99.9%), Ni (99.99%), and Sn (99.99%). The alloys were synthesized from these elements in a MAM-1 compact arc melter under an Ar atmosphere (99.9999% purity). Each sample was remelted three times to improve structural homogeneity. Due to the high reactivity of lanthanum with oxygen, titanium was used as a getter to minimize the oxygen content within the protective Ar atmosphere.

The composition of the experimental alloys was based on the phase diagram [25], focusing on alloys containing the LaNi₅-type phase with an increasing content of either the LaNi₅Sn or LaNiSn phase. The cast specimens had a diameter of approximately 10 mm and a weight of about 1 g. These materials were subsequently sealed in ampoules under a protective Ar atmosphere and annealed at 523 K for 1440 hours to achieve an equilibrium microstructure.

Analysis of microstructure and material properties

The chemical composition of all studied alloys is shown in Table 1. In order to improve the properties of HS while preserving the original microstructures, this material was crushed in a mortar. The resulting powder was sieved through 0.63 μ m sieve.

Structural morphology and chemical analysis were performed using a Tescan LYRA 3 XMU FEG-SEM/FIB microscope, equipped with an Oxford Instruments X-Max80 EDX detector and a Nordlys Nano EBSD detector. Hydrogen kinetic curves and PCT isotherms were measured using a Setaram PCT-Pro E&E Sieverts-type gas sorption analyzer. This device allowed safe, fully-automated, and reproducible measurements in both absorption and desorption regimes using high-purity hydrogen atmosphere (99.9999%).

Figure 1 Ternary phase diagram of the La-Ni-Sn system at 523 K [25], including the labeled compositions of the experimental alloys.

The weight of all samples was about 150 mg. Before the measurements of kinetic curves, the reaction chamber was evacuated to 3×10^{-4} MPa and the samples were heated to selected constant temperatures between 308-373K. Sorption properties were studied under an initial hydrogen pressure of approximately 5×10^{-4} MPa for desorption and 2 MPa for absorption.

The constituent phase and crystalline structure analyses of experimental powders, except sample 30Sn14, were performed by X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) using X'PertPro and Empyrean diffractometer with Co $K\alpha_{1,2}$ radiation. Measurement of XRD patterns of sample 30Sn14 was done using X-ray powder diffractometer Rigaku SmartLab 3kW with Cu $K\alpha_{1,2}$ radiation due to malfunction of Empyrean diffractometer. HighScore Plus 4 software equipped by PDF-2 database (2018) and ICSD database were applied for analysis of X-ray diffraction patterns. The XRD patterns of materials in hydrogenated state were measured at low temperatures close to 263K due to low stability of hydride material at ambient temperature and atmospheric pressure.

Table 1. Chemical composition of experimental materials (EDX).

Sample	Chemical composition (wt. %)		
	La	Ni	Sn
30Sn4	29.5	67.0	3.5
30Sn6	30.0	64.0	6.0
30Sn10	30.0	60.5	9.5
30Sn14	28.0	58.0	14
40Sn11	36.8	51.8	11.4
40Sn24	40.0	36.2	23.8

Computational methods and structure models

For the theoretical analysis, density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed using the Vienna *Ab Initio* Simulation Package (VASP) [23-29], version 6.4.2. The Projector Augmented Wave (PAW) [30,31] method with the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) parametrization of the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) [32,33] was employed to describe the electron exchange–correlation. PAW potentials with the GW extension were utilized to ensure improved accuracy for calculations involving hydrogen. The plane-wave basis set was expanded up to a kinetic energy cutoff of 870 eV. For all optimized structures, a Γ -centered $4 \times 4 \times 5$ k-point grid was used for Brillouin zone sampling. To construct the computational cells, the LaNi_5 unit cell containing six atoms was replicated twice along each crystallographic direction, resulting in a 48-atom supercell. Within this LaNi_5 supercell, Sn atoms were substituted at the Ni 3g sites. Thermodynamic stability analyses were subsequently performed, revealing that among the investigated alloys, $\text{LaNi}_{4.88}\text{Sn}_{0.13}$ and $\text{LaNi}_{4.38}\text{Sn}_{0.63}$ exhibit the highest thermodynamic stability. The structure parameters of these phases are shown in Table 2. These two compositions were therefore selected as basis for the corresponding $\text{H}_7\text{LaNi}_{5-x}\text{Sn}_x$ hydrides. The atomic structures of the calculated phases are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Structures models of $\text{LaNi}_{5-x}\text{Sn}_x$ and $\text{H}_7\text{LaNi}_{5-x}\text{Sn}_x$ phases. Structures were visualized using VESTA software package [34].

Table 2 Structure parameters – equilibrium lattice parameters, volumes, ab-initio

Phase	at.% Sn	wt.% Sn	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³)
$\text{LaNi}_{4.88}\text{Sn}_{0.13}$	2.083	3.374	5.0275	5.0275	4.0081	87.69
$\text{LaNi}_{4.38}\text{Sn}_{0.63}$	10.417	15.790	5.1127	5.1208	4.0846	93.47
$\text{H}_7\text{LaNi}_{4.88}\text{Sn}_{0.13}$	2.083	3.374	5.3862	5.3864	4.3485	109.47
$\text{H}_7\text{LaNi}_{4.38}\text{Sn}_{0.63}$	10.417	15.790	5.5385	5.6195	4.3085	114.22

Results and discussion

Structure of experimental materials

The experimental samples can be categorized into two groups based on La content: those with approximately 30 wt.% La and those with 40 wt.% La, with increasing content of Sn from ~ 4 up to ~ 24 wt.%. The samples are labeled as 30SnX (X = 4, 6, 10, 14) and 40SnX (X = 11, 24), respectively (Table 1).

The annealed alloys were analyzed to verify the element distribution in the microstructure. The elements Ni and La seem to be homogeneously distributed in the alloys 30SnX however Sn segregated into areas with strips-like shape. Due to the high affinity of La to oxygen the microstructure also rarely contained particles of La oxides (Figure 3a,b). Although all experimental materials were prepared under a high-purity protective atmosphere, it was not possible to entirely avoid La oxidation in the laboratory arc melter.

The areas with lower content of Sn were identified as LaNi_5 phase, while areas with higher content of Sn as phase with cell parameters close to phase $\text{LaNi}_{4.7}\text{Sn}_{0.3}$ (Figure 3c,d). Although we had a good fit also with similar phases with content of Sn_x (x=0.2-0.4) for evaluation of content of phases by

Rietveld analysis was used phase $\text{LaNi}_{4.7}\text{Sn}_{0.3}$. These LaNi_5 type phases were difficult to distinguish in XRD patterns due to their highly similar diffraction peaks. Nevertheless, as the Sn content increases in the 30SnX alloys, a slight shift and broadening of the LaNi_5 diffraction peaks toward lower angles is clearly visible, indicating the formation of the $\text{LaNi}_{5-x}\text{Sn}_x$ phases (see peak details in Figure 3d). This shift confirms that higher Sn content expands the unit cell parameters.

The microstructure of the 40SnX alloys exhibited lower chemical homogeneity compared to the 30SnX alloys. Chemical maps of 40SnX alloys showed a correlation between regions with higher La and Sn content, while darker areas indicated lower concentrations of these elements. This correlates well with XRD measurements (Figure 3c, d), where the dark areas with lower Sn and La content are identified as the $\text{LaNi}_5/\text{LaNi}_{4.7}\text{Sn}_{0.3}$ phase (HCP unit cell) [26], and the lighter areas as LaNiSn (orthorhombic unit cell) [27].

Microstructure and hydrogenated alloys

These LaNi_5 -type phases are the primary phases capable to form hydrides during hydrogenation of these alloys. The H_6LaNi_5 -type hydrides (HCP unit cell) [28] are formed from phases $\text{LaNi}_5/\text{LaNi}_{5-x}\text{Sn}_x$ in 30SnX alloys. The measured XRD peaks had very good fit with peaks of $\text{H}_{6,x}\text{LaNi}_5$ ($x=0-0.8$). However, the alloys 40SnX contain also phase LaNiSn due to these alloys contain also hydride H_2LaNiSn (orthorhombic unit cell) [27] after hydrogenation (Figure 3c). The absence of Sn phase peaks during dehydrogenation suggests that the H_6LaNi_5 -type hydrides also incorporate Sn.

Consequently, two types of hydrides likely coexist in the hydrogenated state of 30Sn6–14 alloys: a Sn-free H_6LaNi_5 hydride formed from LaNi_5 , and a Sn-containing H_6LaNi_5 hydride formed from $\text{LaNi}_{4.7}\text{Sn}_{0.3}$. This resulted in enhancing of cell parameters of these types of hydrides, measured by XRD. The dependence of the average cell volumes of H_6LaNi_5 -type phases on the Sn content is shown in Figure 4. The cell parameters and phase fractions evaluated by the Rietveld method are summarized in Table 3. Considering the values of c_{max}^H and content of LaNi_5 -type phases in the structure (Table 3), the composition of hydride phase should be close to H_6LaNi_5 . If the H_7LaNi_5 phase is considered, the value c_{max}^H would be approximately 1.5 wt.% H_2 .

The measured unit cell volumes (Table 3) are compared with values calculated via ab-initio methods (indicated by shadow crosses) and published data for similar alloys annealed at 1223 K for 96–120 h [15]. The volumes of stable phases $\text{LaNi}_{4.88}\text{Sn}_{0.13}$ and $\text{LaNi}_{4.38}\text{Sn}_{0.63}$ (Figure 4) evaluated by ab-initio method fit very well with the published and measured volumes of LaNi_5 -type phases. However, a significant difference exists between alloys annealed at 1223 K [15] and those annealed at 573 K. Due to the miscibility gap (Figure 1) and the coexistence of two LaNi_5 -type phases, the cell volumes do not align with values published for alloys within this miscibility gap region [15]. The volumes of the main phases (LaNi_5 and $\text{LaNi}_{4.7}\text{Sn}_{0.3}$) are similar at the boundaries of the miscibility gap. Outside this

region, the LaNi_5 -type phase exhibits a smaller cell volume due to the coexistence of the LaNiSn phase.

Figure 3 Examples of chemical maps of studied materials, a) 30Sn14, b) 40Sn24 and XRD patterns of experimental alloys, c) hydrogenated d) dehydrogenated, * comparison of chosen peaks of 30SnX alloys.

Table 3 Structural parameters of the LaNi_5 -type phases: cell parameters, unit cell volumes, and phase fractions evaluated by XRD.

Alloy	Cell parameters of phase LaNi_5					Cell parameters of phase $\text{LaNi}_{4.7}\text{Sn}_{0.3}$ (Å)				
	a/b (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³)	c/a (Å)	Phase (%)	a/b (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³)	c/a (Å)	Phase (%)
30Sn4	5.044	4.006	88.269	0.784	78.8	5.038	4.012	88.167	0.796	21.1
30Sn6	5.060	4.009	88.911	0.792	75.2	5.099	4.069	91.663	0.798	24.8
30Sn10	5.057	4.029	89.231	0.796	69.3	5.101	4.108	92.563	0.805	30.7
30Sn14	5.064	4.059	90.036	0.800	22.2	5.108	4.127	93.257	0.808	64.6
40Sn11	5.042	4.000	88.062	0.793	87.3					
40Sn24	5.076	4.039	90.128	0.796	61.3	-	-	-	-	-

The coexistence of LaNi_5 and $\text{LaNi}_{4.7}\text{Sn}_{0.3}$ strongly influences the cell volume of H_6LaNi_5 . The volume increase is slower within the miscibility region due to the simultaneous formation of H_6LaNi_5 hydrides from both phases. This trend mirrors the dependence of H_7LaNi_5 volumes derived from ab-initio calculations and XRD phase analysis. Finally, the H_6LaNi_5 hydride volume in 40SnX alloys is smaller because the formation of the H_2LaNiSn phase reduces the overall influence of Sn on the H_6 -hydride cell volume.

Hydrogen properties of studied alloys

In order to evaluate the sorption properties of experimental materials, kinetics curves and PCT isotherms were measured. The sorption measurements were carried out after four activation sorption cycles at 273K/1h. This activation process was done in order to achieve stable sorption properties.

The equilibrium pressure of hydrogen absorption and desorption decreases with Sn content in the studied alloys. Very strong influence on p_{eq} and the slope of the plateau was observed especially in alloys 30SnX (Figure 5). We can suppose that these changes could be caused by microstructure changes of the AB₅-type phases affected by increasing content of Sn. Due to the limited solubility of Sn in the LaNi₅ phase, the formation of phase LaNi_{5-x}Sn_x started with increasing content of Sn. As was mentioned before, it could be expected that two types of hydride phases are formed in the structure: H₆LaNi₅, one with content of Sn, second without Sn content. This assumption is supported also by the non-formation of a Sn phase in the hydrogenated state (Figure 3c). Due to the similar content of hydrogen in alloys 30LaSn4-10 and LaNi₅ we can expect that the formed hydrides are of the same type. This synergistic effect of these two types of phases caused the strong changes in the PCT curves in comparison with the PCT curve of LaNi₅. Especially, the slope of the plateau is higher than the slope of plateau of LaNi₅ phase. It is more significant in alloys with higher content of Sn. It can be expected that this phenomenon is caused by simultaneous formation/decomposition of two types of H₆LaNi₅ with slightly different values of p_{eq} . It is interesting that the simultaneous decomposition of these hydrides caused at different p_{eq} is beneficial for overcoming the deformation during hydrogen absorption and desorption, resulting in a decrease in difference between absorption and desorption plateau pressures (p_{eq}^a ; p_{eq}^d). The decreased hydrogen capacity observed in alloy 30Sn14 was due to the formation of the LaNi₅Sn phase, which doesn't form hydrides. This resulted in a decreased hydride content in the alloy. The shape of the PCT curves of alloys 40SnX is different due to formation of H₂LaNiSn from the phase LaNiSn. Due to the low content of this phase and formation of the hydride H₆LaNi₅ in alloy 40Sn11 the shape of the PCT curve is similar to PCT curve of the LaNi₅ alloy. The formation of H₂LaNiSn and H₆LaNi₅ is visible in PCT curve of 40Sn24 which caused the formation of two plateaus and also a higher slope of the plateau. The PCT curves were used for evaluation of p_{eq} of hydrides, these values were used for evaluation of enthalpy $\Delta H^{a/d}$, and entropy $\Delta S^{a/d}$ (a – absorption/ d – desorption) of hydrides (formation/decomposition) from the Van't Hoff plot (Figure 6) using the equation

$$\ln \frac{p_{eq}}{p_0} = -\frac{\Delta H^{a/d}}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S^{a/d}}{R}. \quad (1)$$

Figure 5 PCT curves of studied alloys at 50°C.

The values of p_{eq} measured at a variety of temperatures are plotted on a graph with $\ln p_{eq}$ on the y-axis and $1000/T$ on the x axis. From this plot, $\Delta H/R$ is the slope, and $\Delta S/R$ is the intercept of the linear fit (Figure 7). The values of hydrogen absorption and desorption plateau pressures were also used for evaluation of hysteresis (Hys), which represents the difference between these values, which can reflect the energy consumed by the alloy to overcome the deformation during hydrogen absorption and desorption as well as the pulverization of the alloy particles with the cycling. Hysteresis is defined by the equation $Hys = \ln(p_{eq}^a / p_{eq}^d)$ (2), where p_{eq} was evaluated at constant temperature [29]. All values of ΔH , ΔS , p_{eq} and the average value of \overline{Hys} are listed in Table 4.

Figure 6 Van't Hof plot of studied alloys. \bullet $H_2LaNiSn$

Table 4 Enthalpy of hydride H₆LaNiSn formation/decomposition, ¹H₂LaNiSn² [30-33] ³ [22].

Alloy	$\Delta H^{a/d}$, (kJ/mol)	ΔS^a (J/mol·K)	ΔH^d (kJ/mol)	ΔS^d (J/mol·K)	p _{eq} (a/d) (MPa) at 323K	\overline{H}_{ys}
30Sn4	-30.8±2.2	-107.1±6.4	31.2±1.7	107.2±1.7	0.43/0.36	0.15±0.05
30Sn6	-30.7±0.6	-118.0±1.7	30.9±0.6	109.4±1.6	0.18/0.1	0.07±0.05
30Sn10	-31.2±0.6	-115.9±1.9	31.4±0.6	116.1±1.8	0.103/0.098	0.06±0.01
30Sn14	-35.5±0.4	-129.0±1.3	37.3±1.1	133.6±3.8	0.093/0.076	0.15±0.03
40Sn11	-28.2±2.9	-114.9±7.0	31.9±1.2	124.5±4.8	0.29/0.24	0.19±0.04
40Sn24	-34.1±1.2	-132.2±0.7	36.1±0.9	136.8±2.7	0.26/0.21	0.17±0.03
40Sn24 ¹	-39.2±1.2	-134.6±3.7	40.2±1.2	136.0±3.0	0.05/0.04	0.20±0.02
LaNi ₅ ²	~-(28-31)	~-(105-114)	~(28-38)	~(101-114)	~0.69-0.49/0.34-0.12	0.21±0.01
LaNi _{5-x} Sn _x ³	32-36	97-105	35-40	107-110	-	-

The higher values of ΔH of H₆LaNiSn show the higher temperature stability of these hydrides in alloys containing a content of hydride phases H₂LaNiSn or H₆LaNi_{5-x}Sn_x higher than at least 30% of presented phases (see Table 4 and 3). This formation of hydrides H₂LaNiSn (Table 4) or H₆LaNi_{5-x}Sn_x [34] with slightly higher values of $\Delta H^{a/d}$ than H₆LaNiSn causes also higher values of ΔH for this hydride. In the case of alloy 30SnX, the stabilization of hydride H₆LaNi₅ is caused by the simultaneous formation/decomposition of two types of H₆LaNi₅ hydride phases.

The structure changes dependent on the content of Sn significantly influenced also the kinetic of hydrogen sorption. Due to low desorption pressures, it was not possible to reach sufficiently low pressure for the full desorption of almost all studied alloys after absorption measurements. For these reasons, it was not possible to measure kinetic curves of fully desorbed alloys or the pressure was not sufficiently low for a correct measurement of these curves. The representative of kinetic curves of studied alloys at 333K are shown in Fig. 7 a) where is clearly demonstrated that rate of hydrogenation of alloys 30SnX, placed in the miscibility gap region, slowed down in comparison with alloys outside of this region. The decrease in kinetic is very significant, while the alloys 30SnX reach the c_{max}^H at $t = 30-60s$, the alloys 40SnX reach c_{max}^H at about $t > 10-20s$.

The evaluation of activation energy (Ea) from kinetic curves, especially for gas-solid reactions like hydrogen desorption or absorption, was done using the Arrhenius method, which is often applied as the standard iso-conversional method. The Arrhenius method calculates the Ea based on kinetic data measured at various constant temperatures. The theoretical starting point is the general rate equation for solid-gas reactions: $dt/d\alpha = k \cdot f(\alpha)$ (3) where α is the reacted fraction, t is time, k is the rate constant, and $f(\alpha)$ is the mechanism function. The reacted fraction was evaluated by equation $\alpha = c_t^H / c_{max}^H$ (4),

where c_t^H is content of hydrogen at time t and c_{max}^H is total content of hydrogen in alloy at measured constant temperature. Upon integration, this equation yields $f(\alpha)=k \cdot t$ (5). The constant k is a crucial kinetic parameter determined from time-dependent experimental data, specifically kinetic curves that plot α against time t (Fig. 7 b). Various kinetic models (such as the JMAK model, 1D, 2D, 3D or diffusion model) [35] could be applied to the isothermal kinetic curves to calculate the constant k at different temperature T . The constant k was evaluated by the JMAK model, which describes transformation kinetics. In this model, the kinetic constant k for absorption kinetics of kinetic data of hydrogen absorption for the two-phase (α - β) regions were obtained using the following linear form $kt= [-\ln(1-\alpha)]^n$ (8). The slope of this line is the Avrami exponent (n), and the constant k can be determined from the intercept.

The plot of $[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^n$ against t yields a straight line with a very good fit ($r \approx 0.99$), where the exponent n yields values between $1/2-1$ (Fig. 7c). Avrami exponent n values in the range of $0.5-1$ indicate diffusion-controlled kinetics, with suppressed nucleation and growth occurring predominantly from pre-existing nuclei. The constants k are evaluated for various temperatures and show a temperature dependence via the Arrhenius expression:

$$k(T) = k_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (6)$$

where k_0 is the pre-exponential factor, R is the gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature. The Arrhenius equation is then linearized: $\ln k = -E_a/RT + \ln k_0$ (7) and E_a is then determined from the slope of the plot of $\ln k$ versus $1000/T$ (Fig. 7d). The evaluated values of E_a are showed in Table 4 and compared to values of similar alloys and LaNi_5 .

Although the values of E_a slightly decrease with increasing content of Sn in alloys 30SnX , these values are similar to the values E_a in LaNi_5 alloys. This phenomenon could be caused by the increasing difference in cell parameters a/b and c , which are increase with increasing Sn content. This caused structural incoherence of grain boundaries (Gb) between LaNi_5 and $\text{LaNi}_{5-x}\text{Sn}_x$ or H_6LaNi_5 and $\text{H}_6\text{LaNi}_{5-x}\text{Sn}_x$. These structural faults on these Gbs increase Gbs diffusion, which can cause slight decrease of values E_a in these alloys. Despite the fact that the JMAK model was very well-fitted for the evaluation of E_a , the correlation coefficient for the 2D kinetic model increases (from ≈ 0.96 to ≈ 0.98) with higher content of Sn. It support idea that Gb diffusion could contribute to the increase in the kinetics of hydrogen absorption in these alloys.

However, the values of E_a strongly decreased in alloys 40SnX , where two types of hydrides H_6LaNi_5 and H_2LaNiSn are present in the microstructure. Due to different types of cells and cell parameters of these phases the Gb is not coherent, which resultes in faster Gb diffusion [26-28]. This contributes to the lowering of the value E_a in comparison with values of alloys 30SnX . Although the correlation

coefficient of the diffusion kinetic model was close to the JMAK kinetic model, this model shows the best fit.

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 7 Kinetic curves of studied alloys, a) c^H vs t b) α vs t at 333K c) $[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^n$ vs. time for hydriding reaction of the two-phase (α - β) region at 333K d) Arrhenius plot of absorption reaction rate.

Table 4 Activation energy of absorption of studied alloys *[35-38].

Alloys	E_a (kJ/mol)	n
30Sn4	35.7±4.8	1/2-3/4
30Sn6	31.3±4.6	
30Sn10	27.4±3.9	
30Sn14	25.4±1.4	
40Sn11	15.1±3.0	2/3-1
40Sn24	16.7±1.1	
LaNi ₅	19.5-32.2*	-
LmNi _{4.91} Sn _{0.15}	28*	-
LaNi _{4.7} Al _{0.3}	29.1; 36.8*	-

Conclusion

1. Sn substitution in LaNi₅-based alloys significantly influences the structural, thermodynamic, and kinetic properties of hydrogen storage.

- Increasing Sn content expands cell parameters and unit cell volume, thereby reducing equilibrium plateau pressure and enhancing hydride stability.

2. The miscibility gap, present in the La–Ni–Sn phase diagram near the LaNi₅ phase (at ~573 K), significantly affects both enthalpy of hydride formation ΔH and activation energy E_a for hydrogen absorption:

- Effect on enthalpy ΔH : Inside the miscibility gap, two LaNi₅-type phases coexist: LaNi₅ and LaNi_{4.7}Sn_{0.3}. This coexistence leads to the simultaneous formation/decomposition of two hydride phases (H₆LaNi₅ and H₆LaNi_{5-x}Sn_x), which stabilizes the hydride structure. As a result ΔH values indicate higher thermodynamic stability with increasing content of Sn. For alloys within the miscibility gap (e.g., 30Sn14), $\Delta H_a \approx -35.5$ kJ/mol, compared to -30.8 kJ/mol for low-Sn alloys (30Sn4). Outside the miscibility gap (e.g., 40SnX alloys), ΔH values vary due to the formation of additional hydrides (H₂LaNiSn), reaching -39.2 kJ/mol for Sn-rich compositions.

- Effect on activation energy E_a : In the miscibility gap (30SnX alloys), E_a decreases moderately with Sn content: From 35.7 kJ/mol (30Sn4) to 25.4 kJ/mol (30Sn14). This reduction is linked to structural incoherence at the grain boundaries between the LaNi₅ and LaNi_{5-x}Sn_x phases, which enhances grain boundary diffusion. Outside the miscibility gap (40SnX alloys), E_a drops sharply: Down to 15–16 kJ/mol, due to coexistence of hydrides with different crystal structures (H₆LaNi₅ and H₂LaNiSn), creating more non-coherent grain boundaries and accelerating diffusion. Avrami exponent n values in the range of 0.5–1 indicate diffusion-controlled kinetics, with suppressed nucleation and growth occurring predominantly from pre-existing nuclei.

3. Alloys with a higher Sn content exhibit reduced hysteresis and despite a slight decrease in maximum hydrogen capacity.

Acknowledgment

This paper was created as part of the project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631 Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komensky Operational Program financed by the European Union and from the state budget of the Czech Republic and the paper was also supported by the Institute of Physics of Materials AS CR, CZ-61662 Brno, Czech Republic, program Strategy AV21, program Sustainable energy; Project: Hydrogen technologies AV21/27.

Data Availability Statement: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18000231>

References:

- [1] Schlapbach L, Züttel A. Hydrogen-storage materials for mobile applications. *Nature* 2001;414:353–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35104634>.
- [2] Züttel A. Materials for hydrogen storage. *Materials Today* 2003;6:24–33. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-7021\(03\)00922-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1369-7021(03)00922-2).
- [3] Wei TY, Lim KL, Tseng YS, Chan SLI. A review on the characterization of hydrogen in hydrogen storage materials. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2017;79:1122–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.05.132>.
- [4] Zeaiter A, Nardin P, Pour Yazdi MA, Billard A. Outstanding shortening of the activation process stage for a TiFe-based hydrogen storage alloy. *Materials Research Bulletin* 2019;112:132–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.materresbull.2018.12.015>.
- [5] Shang H, Li Y, Zhang Y, Zhao D, Qi Y, Xu X. Investigations on hydrogen storage performances and mechanisms of as-cast TiFe_{0.8}Ni_{0.2}Co (m=0, 0.03, 0.05 and 0.1) alloys. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2021;46:17840–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2021.02.179>.
- [6] Panwar K, Srivastava S. On structural model of AB₅-type multi-element hydrogen storage alloy. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2019;44:30208–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.09.138>.
- [7] Latroche M, Percheron-Guégan A, Notten PHL. Structural, thermodynamic and electrochemical properties of over-stoichiometric La_{1-y}(Ni_{1-z}Sn_z)_{5+2y} hydride forming compounds. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 2004;377:133–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2004.01.026>.
- [8] Aadhithiyar AK, Anbarasu S. Experimental studies on a micron-copper powder enhanced multi-helical AB₅ hydrogen storage reactor: Challenges and pathways to improved design. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2025;142:341–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.05.437>.
- [9] Milanese C, Jensen TR, Hauback BC, Pistidda C, Dornheim M, Yang H, et al. Complex hydrides for energy storage. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2019;44:7860–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2018.11.208>.
- [10] Briki C, Belkhiria S, Dhaou MH, De Rango P, Jemni A. Experimental study of the influences substitution from Ni by Co, Al and Mn on the hydrogen storage properties of LaNi_{3.6}Mn_{0.3}Al_{0.4}Co_{0.7} alloy. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2017;42:10081–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.02.065>.
- [11] Willems JJG, Buschow KHJ. From permanent magnets to rechargeable hydride electrodes. *Journal of the Less Common Metals* 1987;129:13–30. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5088\(87\)90029-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5088(87)90029-4).
- [12] Bowman RC, Luo CH, Ahn CC, Witham CK, Fultz B. The effect of tin on the degradation of LaNi₅-Sn metal hydrides during thermal cycling. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 1995;217:185–92. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0925-8388\(94\)01337-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0925-8388(94)01337-3).
- [13] Ratnakumar BV, Witham C, Fultz B, Halpert G. Electrochemical Evaluation of La-Ni-Sn Metal Hydride Alloys. *J Electrochem Soc* 1994;141:L89–91. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.2055105>.
- [14] Cantrell JS, Beiter TA, Bowman RC. Crystal structure and hydriding behavior of LaNi_{5-y}Sn_y. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 1994;207–208:372–6. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0925-8388\(94\)90242-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0925-8388(94)90242-9).
- [15] Joubert J-M, Latroche M, Černý R, Bowman RC, Percheron-Guégan A, Yvon K. Crystallographic study of LaNi_{5-x}Sn_x (0.2 ≤ x ≤ 0.5) compounds and their hydrides. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 1999;293–295:124–9. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8388\(99\)00311-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8388(99)00311-4).
- [16] Vogt T, Reilly JJ, Johnson JR, Adzic GD, McBreen J. ChemInform Abstract: Crystal Structure of Nonstoichiometric La(Ni,Sn)_{5+x} Alloys and Their Properties as Metal Hydride Electrodes. *ChemInform* 1999;30:chin.199919021. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chin.199919021>.

- [17] Deng H, Zhuang Y, Liu J, Guo J, Lü J, Yan J. Electrochemical performance of LaNi_{5-x}Sn_x alloys. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 2004;376:211–4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2003.12.026>.
- [18] Hughes J. Positional disorder in LaNi₅–ySn_y intermetallic phases. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 1997;22:347–9. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-3199\(96\)00170-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0360-3199(96)00170-X).
- [19] Luo S, Clewley JD, Flanagan TB, Bowman RC, Wade LA. Further studies of the isotherms of LaNi_{5-x}Sn_x–H for x=0–0.5. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 1998;267:171–81. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8388\(97\)00536-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8388(97)00536-7).
- [20] Coene W, Notten PHL, Hakkens F, Einerhand REF, Daams JLC. Transmission electron microscopy study of order-disorder phenomena in non-stoichiometric LaNi_{5+x} and LaNi_{6-x} Cux electrode materials. *Philosophical Magazine A* 1992;65:1485–502. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01418619208205618>.
- [21] Young K, Fetcenko MA, Ouchi T, Li F, Koch J. Effect of Sn-substitution in C14 Laves phase alloys for NiMH battery application. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 2009;469:406–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2008.01.134>.
- [22] Borzone EM, Baruj A, Blanco MV, Meyer GO. Dynamic measurements of hydrogen reaction with LaNi_{5-x}Sn_x alloys. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2013;38:7335–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2013.04.035>.
- [23] Zhu Z, Zhu S, Lu H, Wu J, Yan K, Cheng H, et al. Stability of LaNi₅-Co alloys cycled in hydrogen — Part 1 evolution in gaseous hydrogen storage performance. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2019;44:15159–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2019.04.111>.
- [24] Blanco MV, Borzone EM, Baruj A, Meyer GO. Hydrogen sorption kinetics of La–Ni–Sn storage alloys. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2014;39:5858–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2014.01.125>.
- [25] Zobač O, Zizka R, Richter KW, Smetana B, Zla S, Kawulokova M, et al. Experimental Study of the Phase Diagram of the La-Ni-Sn System at 300 and 600 °C 2025. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5228280>.
- [26] Král L, Chesalkin A, Cermak J, Roupčova P, Prusov E. Influence of Fe on the Hydrogen Storage Properties of LaCeNi Alloys. *Langmuir* 2023;39:6061–8. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.langmuir.3c00093>.
- [27] Aburto A, Orgaz E. *Ab initio* structural and electronic investigation of magnetic R Ni Sn (R = La , Ce , Pr , Nd) intermetallics and their hydrides. *Phys Rev B* 2007;75:045130. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.75.045130>.
- [28] Lushnikov SA, Filippova TV. LaNi₅- and RT₃-based (R = Ce, Nd, Gd, Er; T = Co, Ni, Fe) hydrides prepared at low temperatures and H₂ pressures. *Inorg Mater* 2013;49:770–4. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0020168513080104>.
- [29] Flanagan TB, Park C-N, Oates WA. Hysteresis in solid state reactions. *Progress in Solid State Chemistry* 1995;23:291–363. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0079-6786\(95\)00006-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0079-6786(95)00006-G).
- [30] Liu W, Aguey-Zinsou K-F. Synthesis of highly dispersed nanosized LaNi₅ on carbon: Revisiting particle size effects on hydrogen storage properties. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2016;41:14429–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2016.02.024>.
- [31] Joubert J-M, Paul-Boncour V, Cuevas F, Zhang J, Laroche M. LaNi₅ related AB₅ compounds: Structure, properties and applications. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 2021;862:158163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2020.158163>.
- [32] Liu W, Aguey-Zinsou K-F. Low temperature synthesis of LaNi₅ nanoparticles for hydrogen storage. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2016;41:1679–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2015.10.128>.
- [33] Xu J, Chen X, Zhu W, Zhang W, Cui H, Zhu S, et al. Enhanced cycling stability and reduced hysteresis of AB₅-type hydrogen storage alloys by partial substitution of Sn for Ni. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2022;47:22495–509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.05.071>.
- [34] Chandra Mouli B, Sharma VK, Sanjay, Paswan M, Thomas B. Performance investigations on thermochemical energy storage system using cerium, aluminium, manganese, and tin-substituted

- LaNi₅ hydrides. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2024;96:1203–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.11.354>.
- [35] Li Q, Lin Q, Chou K-C, Jiang L. A study on the hydriding-dehydriding kinetics of Mg_{1.9}Al_{0.1}Ni. *Journal of Materials Science* 2004;39:61–5. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:JMSE.0000007728.04363.8c>.
- [36] Koh JT, Goudy AJ, Huang P, Zhou G. A comparison of the hydriding and dehydriding kinetics of LaNi₅ hydride. *Journal of the Less Common Metals* 1989;153:89–100. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5088\(89\)90536-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5088(89)90536-5).
- [37] Pan Y-B, Wu Y-F, Li Q. Modeling and analyzing the hydriding kinetics of Mg–LaNi₅ composites by Chou model. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2011;36:12892–901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2011.06.145>.
- [38] Muthukumar P, Satheesh A, Linder M, Mertz R, Groll M. Studies on hydriding kinetics of some La-based metal hydride alloys. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy* 2009;34:7253–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2009.06.075>.